

Synthesis of copper(II) toluate adducts with substituted morpholines

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Manuscript received 1 October 2002, accepted 27 February 2003

Some new complexes of Cu(RCOO)₂ (where R = 4-CH₃C₆H₄, 3-CH₃C₆H₄ and 2-CH₃C₆H₄) with the saturated diheterocyclic bases (L-L) = 4-methylmorpholine, 4-ethylmorpholine and 2,6-dimethylmorpholine have been synthesized. All the complexes are antiferromagnetic with these bases. Their stoichiometries are of the type Cu(RCOO)₂ (B)_n (B = L-L and n = 1 or 0.5). The spin exchange parameter, -2J, for some complexes has been evaluated from magnetic susceptibility measurements at different temperatures and for other complexes from EPR spectral measurements at different temperatures.

The influence of the steric and electronic characteristics of pyridine type ligands on the structural and magnetic properties of their complexes with copper(II) carboxylates have been the subject of systematic investigations^{1,2}, but no reports exist on saturated diheterocyclic bases. In the present study, the complexation properties of 4-methylmorpholine (4-MeMorph), 4-ethylmorpholine (4-EtMorph) and 2,6-dimethylmorpholine (2,6-Me₂Morph) with copper(II) toluates have been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The adducts of copper(II) toluates with substituted morpholines were synthesized by reacting their ethereal solutions in stoichiometric amount and 50% excess of heterocyclic base, whereby complexes with 1 : 0.5 and 1 : 1 stoichiometry were obtained by the following equations. Copper(II) toluates were prepared by reacting copper(II) sulfate with stoichiometric amount of sodium salts of the corresponding toluic acids in water-acetone mixture.

where n = 2, 3 or 4

and L = 4-MeMorph, 4-EtMorph and 2,6-Me₂Morph

when x = 1

and L = 2,6-Me₂Morph when n = 0.5.

The complexes (Table 1) are insoluble in organic sol-

Table 1. Analytical data, colour and amount of the base used*

Compd.	Cu%: Found (Calcd.)	Colour	Sa/ Excess**
Cu(4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (4-MeMorph)	14.83 (14.61)	Green	E
Cu(4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ (4-EtMorph)	14.22 (14.15)	Blue	E
Cu(4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (2,6-Me ₂ Morph)	14.30 (14.15)	Sky blue	Sa
Cu(4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	16.04 (16.24)	Pale blue	Sa
Cu(3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (4-MeMorph)	14.80 (14.61)	Green	E
Cu(3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (4-EtMorph)	13.63 (14.15)	Dark blue	E
Cu(3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (2,6-Me ₂ Morph)	14.05 (14.15)	Blue	E
Cu(3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	15.89 (16.24)	Bluish green	Sa
Cu(2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (2,6-Me ₂ Morph)	13.92 (14.15)	Pale green	Sa
Cu(2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂ · (2,6-Me ₂ Morph) _{0.5}	15.18 (16.24)	Dark green	Sa

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

**Indicates as to whether the heterocyclic base was taken in stoichiometric amount (Sa) or in excess (E).

vents and decompose above 250°. The interest in the present investigations was to see the role of p*K*_a of the parent carboxylic acid in structure determination and the effect of steric and electronic properties of the six-membered saturated diheterocyclic bases on the stoichiometry, magnetic behavior and structure of complexes.

IR spectra :

Since both the carboxylate group and the diheterocyclic base can coordinate to the metal ion in a bidentate or monodentate fashion, many structural arrangements, are possible in principle³. Various structural possibilities for complexes of the stoichiometries $\text{Cu}(\text{RCOO})_2(\text{L})_x$ (where $x = 0.5$ or 1) depend upon the mode of coordination of carboxylate group and the diheterocyclic bases. IR studies are quite useful in determining the mode of coordination of these ligands^{1,4}. On critically examining the positions and direction of the shifts of the $\nu_a(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{OCO})$ of the carboxylate group in the complexes, as compared to their positions in the sodium salts of the respective acids, the bridging bidentate mode of coordination of the carboxylate group has been suggested for all the complexes^{4,5}. An examination of the spectra of all the complexes reveals a close similarity to those of the free bases and no new bands of low or medium intensity (characteristic of boat configuration)⁶ appear at $1500\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, thus indicating the bases to be coordinated in the same form as they exist in the free state, i.e. in the chair form. A band observed around 1100 cm^{-1} (COC) in free morpholine ligands undergoes a negative shift of $5\text{--}25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in some complexes which suggests coordination of these bases through oxygen atom. The band due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ in the complexes of the base 2,6-Me₂Morph appears at lower wavenumber ($3300\text{--}3290\text{ cm}^{-1}$) relative to its position in the free base (3335 cm^{-1}), indicating the coordination of the amine through the nitrogen atom of its N-H bond. Additional bands in the complexes, compared with the far-IR spectra of uncomplexed copper(II) toluates and free bases in the regions $480\text{--}380$ and $312\text{--}275\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have tentatively been assigned to $\nu_{\text{Cu-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ modes, respectively⁷.

Electronic reflectance spectra :

The complexes under study show a broad band in the region $14705\text{--}13515\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their electronic reflectance spectra. It is a composite band (band-I) and is considered to contain bands due to the $d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions for Cu^{II} ion in tetragonal environment. The band-II which appears as a shoulder at $33335\text{--}37035\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to charge transfer transition $2p\pi(\text{O}) \rightarrow (d_{x^2-y^2})^*$.

EPR spectra :

The X-band room-temperature EPR spectra of powdered samples of all the complexes exhibit three electron paramagnetic resonance absorption lines around field strengths 600, 4700 and 6100 G, which are characteristic of the spin-triplet state ($S = 1$) in the axial symmetry of the binuclear complexes and correspond respectively to the resonance fields H_{z1} , H_{z1} and H_{z2} with $D > hv$ and $E = 0$ ^{8,9}, the

zero-field splitting parameters for the triplet state. That these complexes do not seem to undergo rhombic distortion is confirmed by the absorption line (as seen in three of the complexes) at 4700 G (H_{z1}) not splitting even at low temperatures. The ranges of the parameters g_{\parallel} or g_z (2.41–2.46), g_{\perp} (2.10–2.14) and D (0.35–0.40) evaluated from the EPR spectra are comparable with the earlier reported values for binuclear copper(II) carboxylate complexes^{1,10,11}. In the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{3-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2(\text{2,6-Me}_2\text{Morph})_{0.5}$ at low temperature (113 K), the band around 600 G (H_{z1}) is split into seven lines having intensity ratio $1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 3 : 2 : 1$ due to hyperfine coupling of nuclear spin of two copper ions with the electron spin ($2nI + 1$ lines; $n = 2$ and $I = 3/2$ for ⁶³Cu). The observed value of A_{\parallel} is found to be about one-half (0.006816 cm^{-1}) of that generally observed for magnetically dilute copper(II) complexes in similar environment. The value of A_{\parallel} lies close to the values already reported for binuclear copper(II) carboxylate complexes. This observation further supports the magnetic exchange taking place between two metal ions (in the spin-spin coupled^{9,12} complexes).

In addition to the above-mentioned absorptions, an absorption line around 3200 G is also observed. The intensity of this line increases while that due to the triplet state, as expected, decreases with the lowering of temperature. This line is, therefore, attributed to the magnetically dilute copper(II) impurity which is commonly present in the copper(II) arylcarboxylate complexes^{8,13,14}.

Magnetic susceptibility :

The room-temperature μ_{eff} values for all the copper(II) complexes lie in the range 1.32–1.67 B.M. which is less than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) for one unpaired electron. These values are, however, close to that reported for dinuclear or polynuclear copper(II) carboxylate complexes in which carboxylate group acts as a bridge between two metal ions¹⁰ and spin-spin interaction exists.

Three of the complexes have also been characterized by magnetic susceptibility measurements at different temperatures. The magnetic moment for these complexes decrease with temperature, thus confirming their antiferromagnetic behavior. But the susceptibility for $\text{Cu}(\text{4-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2(\text{2,6-Me}_2\text{Morph})$ increases with temperature while for the other two complexes it decreases. This behavior suggests that either $\text{Cu}(\text{4-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2(\text{2,6-Me}_2\text{Morph})$ has a spin-exchange parameter ($-2J$) considerably smaller than the other two complexes, or it has a much higher proportion of magnetically dilute impurity, which is commonly found in antiferromagnetic complexes. Hence the following modified equation based upon Bleaney and Bowers¹⁵ model, which takes into consideration the presence of

a paramagnetic impurity, was employed to evaluate the spin-exchange parameter ($-2J$) from magnetic susceptibility data at different temperatures^{13,14},

$$\ln \left(\frac{N\bar{g}^2\beta^2(1-x)}{kT \left(\chi_{Cu} - \frac{0.43x}{T} - N\alpha \right)} - 3 \right) = -2J/kT$$

$$\text{or } \ln(F-3) = -2J/kT$$

The unknown quantities in the above expression on the L.H.S. were as follows: the value of \bar{g} was determined from EPR measurements and the value of $N\alpha$ was taken to be 60×10^{-6} c.g.s. units. The value of x (the mole fraction of paramagnetic impurity) was so chosen as to give the best fit with the above expression. The values of $-2J$ were obtained from the slope [$2J/k$] of the straight-line obtained from plots of $\ln(F-3)$ vs $1/T$. The value of $-2J$ was also calculated for some complexes from the variation of intensity (I) of the EPR lines at temperatures 223, 173 and 113 K using the relation^{8,14},

$$A_1/A_2 = I_1/I_2 = \frac{T_2(3 + e^{-2j/kT_2})}{T_1(3 + e^{-2j/kT_1})}$$

The relative areas of curves [A_1/A_2] at two different temperatures (T_1 and T_2) were estimated by the reported methods¹⁶. The values of $-2J$ determined by the two methods are comparable and lie at $224-314 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The values of $-2J$ do not vary much among the complexes and hence no consistent trend of the variation of $-2J$ with pK_{as} of the acids or the electronic nature of the axial ligands is obtained. Moreover, this range of values for $-2J$ of the present complexes with axial ligands having high donor ability (saturated amines) is comparable with other aromatic nitrogen donor axial ligands (pyridine or quinoline etc.) with less donor ability.

Copper(II) acetate monohydrate-like dinuclear structure¹⁷ for complexes of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{RCOO})_2(\text{L-L})$ and the $\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2(\text{dioxane})_{0.5}$ like polymeric structure¹⁸ with syn-syn bridging carboxylate groups forming dinuclear units, connected by L-L bases, for complexes of the type $\text{Cu}(\text{RCOO})_2(\text{L-L})_{0.5}$ are proposed. The results of the present study show that steric hindrance of the amine ligands plays an important role in determining the stoichiometry and structure of the complexes whereby the 2,6-dimethyl-morpholine affords complexes with stoichiometries both 1 : 1 and 1 : 0.5 (metal-base). The 4-methyl and 4-ethyl-morpholines provide complexes of only 1 : 1 stoichiometry. These bases

yield the complexes which are all antiferro-magnetic in nature.

Experimental

The bases 4-methylmorpholine, 4-ethylmorpholine and 2,6-dimethylmorpholine (Aldrich) were dried by refluxing over NaOH beads. The colourless liquids obtained after distillation were stored over NaOH beads.

Copper(II) toluates (ortho-, meta- and para-) : Toluic acid (Sisco; 5 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of acetone was treated with a solution of NaOH (Merck; 1.469 g) in distilled water. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5 by adding appropriate amount of toluic acid. The filtered solution of copper(II) sulfate (Merck; 4.585 g) in distilled water was then added to the stirred solution of sodium toluate. The resulting solid was washed with distilled water and dried in air. It was then dried at 110° for 2 h.

The complexes : To copper(II) toluate (1 g) taken as its suspension in ether (30 cm^3), solution of stoichiometric amount or 50% excess (Table 1) of heterocyclic base in the same solvent (15 cm^3) was added dropwise with stirring for 2 h, and then further stirred for 2 h. The separated solid product was washed with acetone and solvent ether, dried under vacuum and placed in a desiccator containing anhydrous calcium chloride.

Copper was determined volumetrically by EDTA. C and H were analysed on a Coleman-33 analyzer, while nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer and electronic reflectance spectra (either neat or diluted with an appropriate amount of MgCO_3) on a Unicam SP-700 spectrophotometer having SP-735 diffuse reflectance attachment ($50000-4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The X-band EPR measurements ($9.439 - 9.442 \text{ GHz}$) of powdered materials at room temperature were made on a JES-FE3XG spectrometer and X-band EPR measurements ($8.916-9.190 \text{ GHz}$) of powdered materials at different temperatures were made on a Varian E-4 spectrometer. Diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used as a calibrant.

Room temperature magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. The magnetic susceptibility of the three complexes at different temperatures was measured on a PAR-155 instrument. The measured susceptibility was corrected for the diamagnetic susceptibility of the ligands. The correction for temperature independent paramagnetism was taken as -60×10^{-6} c.g.s. units per g-atom of copper(II) ions.

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